

**ANTH 130 Archaeology:
Lessons from the Past**
Time: T & Th, 1:30–2:45 PM
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu
Office Hours: On Zoom,
Wednesday 10–12 & by appointment

In US popular culture, the word “archaeology” often conjures up images of buried treasure, ancient ruins, daring adventurers, and perhaps even dinosaurs¹ or aliens². In reality, the discipline of archaeology is the study of the material traces of the human past. These traces include everything from human-made objects such as pottery, stone tools, and architecture, to animal bones, plant remains, and human skeletons. Rather than seeking out individual artifacts because of their aesthetic or monetary value (*cough, cough* Indiana Jones, *cough, cough*), archaeologists excavate and analyze artifacts and remains because they provide evidence of how past people lived and how ancient societies were organized.

Archaeology is important because it allows us to access the entire scope of human history, from the Paleolithic to the present day, providing us with an understanding of what it means to be human across space and over time. This does not, however, mean that archaeology is a value-free discipline; instead, archaeological questions are shaped by history and culture. In this course, we will critically examine how archaeologists ask and answer questions about the human past, while exploring how their research is received in popular culture.

Class Structure

All class lectures will be pre-recorded on Zoom. No live discussions or activities will be recorded. There will be two tracks for this class:

- (A) entirely remote;
- (B) hybrid remote and in-person, meeting approximately once a week for 30 minutes of discussion or activities as long as safety allows.

There will be no penalties for choosing a particular track or for switching between tracks over the course of the semester, but you need to let me know in advance so that I can work out the logistics.

¹ Nope.
² An even bigger nope.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of this course students will be able to:

- Describe how and why archaeological sites are formed
- Explain how and why archaeological sites are and are not excavated
- Explain how archaeologists collect data in order to learn about the past
- Understand how archaeological research differs from artifact collecting
- Explain the importance of using multiple lines of evidence when studying the past
- Critically evaluate how archaeological research is received in popular culture
- Apply archaeological information to contemporary social problems

Textbook & Readings

The textbook for this course is:

Renfrew, C. & Bahn, P. (2018). *Archaeology essentials: Theory/methods/practice* (4th ed.). New York: Thames & Hudson.

The 3rd edition is also acceptable. The textbook is available through the Vassar College bookstore. All other assigned readings will be posted as pdfs on Moodle.

Grading

Your grade in this course will be based on four primary components:

Participation (20%)	Blog posts (20%)
Exams (40%)	Paper (20%)

Final course grades will be assigned using a 100-point scale. Vassar does not assign a grade of A+; an “A” grade is ≥ 95 points. A failing grade is ≤ 62 points. Grades will be rounded up or down to the nearest integer.

A- = 90–94

B+ = 87–89

B = 83–86

B- = 80–82

C+ = 77–79

C = 73–76, etc., etc.

Schedule of Exam and Paper Deadlines

Assignment	Date
Midterm Exam	Tuesday October 13–Thursday, October 15
Paper	Friday, November 20
Final Exam	TBD—Exam Period

Schedule of Blog Post Deadlines

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Post 1	Friday, Sep 18	Friday, Sep 25	Friday, Oct 2	Friday, Oct 9
Post 2	Friday, Oct 23	Friday, Oct 30	Friday, Nov 7	Friday, Nov 12

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be points during the semester when you are unable to meet class deadlines. I am giving each of you **3 “grace days”** to use as you see fit over the course of the semester. Each grace day offers a full 24-hour extension and can be used for any assignment except the midterm and final exam. You will need to email me in advance of the assignment due date to let me know that you will be using a grace day, but you do not need to explain or justify its use.

If you use up all of your grace days and you need an extension for an emergency reason (illness, family or personal issues, etc.) please email me or visit with me during Zoom office hours; given the past six months I am inclined to be flexible. The same thing goes for absences during in-person discussion/activities or remote discussion/activities.

Grading Structure

Engagement (20%)

Engagement points will be earned by demonstrating that you are actively interacting with course material and conversations. Because of the unpredictable nature of the coming semester, engagement may be assessed in a variety of ways, ranging from written responses to worksheets and handouts, posting on online discussion boards, taking online quizzes, or conducting virtual or in-person conversations.

Whatever the format, being an engaged member of this class means that you will regularly contribute to discussion (whatever the format), including asking questions, responding to others’ questions, offering and defending your own opinions, and generally helping move the class towards new levels of understanding without dominating the discussion. Your overall course engagement will receive a single grade based on the following criteria: absent for more than five in-person classes or remote equivalents (0 pts), passive (10 pts), occasionally active (15 pts), or regularly active (20 pts). If you are having issues with accruing multiple absences for emergency reasons, please contact me to let me know—see the COVID-19 note above.

Blog posts = 20% (2 posts, 20 % each)

This course will use a WordPress blog to create a series of posts sharing what we have learned about archaeology with the rest of the world. You will need to complete one post before the midterm exam, and one post after the midterm exam, following the posting schedule for your assigned group. There are a variety of options for post format. These include:

- Audio (exactly 4 minutes)
- Video (exactly 4 minutes)
- Written text (400–500 words)

All blog posts must conform to the blog post requirements detailed in the table below. The point of the posts is to demonstrate how you can use the course content (from the assigned posting week) to understand or explain some aspect of the past or present not covered in the assigned readings or lecture material. **Students are strongly advised to work with the course assistant to refine their posts before they are published.** It is the student's responsibility to post their own contributions to the WordPress blog.

Blog post requirements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Post title• Two images with captions• Reference list• Posts must be original work citing sources using links to or academic citations of original content (textbooks, image sources, etc).• Citations and reference lists must follow the ANTH 130 Written Assignment Formatting Guidelines.

Exams = 40% (2 exams, 20% each)

There will be a midterm and a final exam, each worth 20% of your grade. These exams will assess your understanding of lectures, course readings, and the participation component of the class. Half of the exam questions will be drawn from course readings, and half will come from lectures and the participation component of the class. The Renfrew & Bahn textbook provides study tools through the publisher's website³, and the end of each textbook chapter contains study questions. Use these tools to prepare for exam questions from these readings.

Paper = 20%

You will write one 800–1000-word paper during this class. Paper topics and assignment details will be introduced by the fourth week of class.

Papers should be submitted by email to jessicabeck@vassar.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the paper for this class should be submitted by midnight on Friday, November 20, meaning that you will have all day Friday to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by one point for the first 24 hours, then two points per each subsequent day. See the COVID-19 Note on p.3 for information about grace days and extensions.

Office Hours

Office hours will be held on Zoom from 10:00–12:00 every Wednesday, with additional Zoom office hours scheduled by appointment for students who cannot make that time slot. To attend office hours, please make an appointment on my Google Calendar so that multiple students are not trying to meet with me simultaneously. A link to the Google Appointments page for office hours is posted on Moodle. Appointment slots will be for 20-minute increments. If you think that you will need more time to discuss a particular issue, please email me in advance.

³ <https://digital.wwnorton.com/archess4>

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and exams, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here:

<https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Accessibility Accommodations

If you have a condition that requires special accommodations, please have it documented by the Office for Accessibility and Educational Opportunity and provide me with a copy of your AEO accommodation letter before your accommodations are needed.

Title IX Responsibilities

All Vassar faculty members are “responsible employees;” if you inform a member of the faculty about a situation involving sexual harassment, sexual assault, relationship abuse, or stalking, they must share that information with the Title IX Coordinator. After a notification, the Title IX office will only provide outreach by email, meaning that you will control how your case will be handled—you do not have to read or reply to the email. It is entirely your decision whether or not to pursue a formal complaint.

Image Credits for First Page

1. Miquitos. Stonehenge at Dawn, Wiltshire, England [Online image]. Flickr. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/12333120@N00/3679952184>
2. Hellier, Chris. Historical Tourists at Stonehenge (2013). [Online Image] Corbis vis Getty Images. <https://www.historyextra.com/period/prehistoric/stonehenge-a-prehistoric-tourist-trap/>
3. SH Numbers (2016). [Online Image]. Heritage Action. <https://heritageaction.wordpress.com/2016/05/13/stonehenge-visitor-numbers-how-many-is-too-many/>

Image Credits for Course Topics

1. Trowel [Online image]. (2020). Pixabay. <https://pixabay.com/vectors/trowel-black-silhouette-tool-309913/>
2. Total station [Online image]. (2020). 123rf. https://www.123rf.com/clipart-vector/total_station.html?sti=m8vvgf3iux26qvkczy
3. Frere, John. (1800). Handaxe. [Online image]. Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hand_axe.
4. Pine Tree [Online image] (2019). KindPNG. https://www.kindpng.com/imgv/TwRxi_pine-tree-silhouette-transparent-background-hd-png-download/;
5. Brain [Online image]. (2019). NetClipart https://www.netclipart.com/isee/iTTxoT_png-transparent-images-pluspng-icon-image-brain-image/;
6. Bridge of Stones [Online image]. (2020). CashAdvance6Online <http://www.cashadvance6online.com/bridge-of-stones-wallpapers/997684069.html>
7. Pyramids [Online image]. (2020). HiClipart: <https://www.hiclipart.com/free-transparent-background-png-clipart-dfwgn>
8. Mandible traced from Buikstra, J., & Ubelaker, D. (1994). *Standards for Data Collection from Human Skeletal Remains*. Fayetteville: Arkansas Archeological Survey Research Series No. 44
9. Rabbit [Online image]. (2019). NetClipart. https://www.netclipart.com/isee/miwRbm_bunny-hopping-rabbit-jump-silhouette-gif/;
10. Mississippian jar depicting a frog [Online image] (2020). National Museum of the American Indian. <https://americanindian.si.edu/static/exhibitions/infinityofnations/woodlands/056528.html>;
11. Question mark [Online image]. (2020). PNGWING. <https://www.pngwing.com/en/free-png-zolrn>;
12. Image of unbalanced scales [Online image]. (2018). Pinclipart https://www.pinclipart.com/pindetail/TmbowT_image-of-unbalanced-scales-rule-of-law-png/
13. Books stack of three [Online image]. (2010–2020). FlatIcon https://www.flaticon.com/free-icon/books-stack-of-three_29302

COURSE SCHEDULE

* = Classes for this week will be held remotely.

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change the readings, activities, and discussion if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course.

Week 1. September 1 + September 3
Course overview and introduction to archaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Preface + Ch. 1

Week 2. September 8 + September 10
Archaeological insights: How sites are created and discovered

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 2 + Ch. 3; Beck 2015

Week 3. September 15 + September 17
Stuff and nonsense: The archaeology of material culture

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 4 + Ch.7; Rathje & Murphy 1992
Group 1 first blog posts due Friday, September 18

Week 4. September 22 + September 24
Pathways to the past: Reconstructing the environment

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 6; Cannon & Cannon 2004; Steadman 1995
Group 2 first blog posts due Friday, September 25

Week 5. September 29 + October 1
Where is my mind? Social and cognitive archaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 5 + Ch.9; The Arch & Anth Podcast Episode #143
Group 3 first blog posts due Friday, October 2

Week 6. October 6 + October 8
Explanations and ownership: The public and the past

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 10 + Ch. 11 + Ch. 12
Group 4 first blog posts due Friday, October 9

Community Care Day, Wednesday October 3

***Week 7. October 13 + October 15**
Archaeology vs. Pseudoarchaeology and Midterm Review

Readings: Parker 2016; Feder 2020

MIDTERM EXAM: October 13–October 15

Week 8. October 20 + October 22
Peopling the past: Bioarchaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 8; Overholtzer & Argueta 2017;
LaRoche & Blakey 1997; Robb 2009
Group 1 second blog posts due Friday, October 23

Week 9. October 27 + October 29
Fun with fauna: The archaeology of animals

Readings: Harris and Cipolla 2017; Morey 2006;
O'Connor 2013 (Introduction + Ch. 13); Thomas and Waterman 2013
Group 2 second blog posts due Friday, October 30

***Week 10. November 5**
Deep roots: The archaeology of plants

Readings: Fisher 2020; Twiss 2007

Community Care Day, Tuesday November 3

Group 3 second blog posts due Friday, November 7

Week 11. November 10 + November 12
Archaeology today: Modern problems, ancient solutions?

Readings: De León 2012; Groesbek et al. 2014; Lentz et al. 2018
Optional Reading: Crabtree et al. 2017
Group 4 second blog posts due Friday, November 12

Week 12. November 17 + November 19
The Archaeology of Native North America & Thanksgiving

Readings: Bugos 2019; Leonard et al. 2020; Timmerman 2020
Optional Reading: Schilling 2012
Friday, November 20 ANTH-130 paper due

THANKSGIVING BREAK
Saturday November 21—Sunday November 29

***Week 13. December 1 + December 3**
The archaeology of inequality; the inequality of archaeology

Readings: Beck 2020; The Arch & Anth Podcast Episode #64 (under Rivera in Reading List); White and Draycott 2020
Optional Reading: Moser 2007

***Week 14. December 8**
Review for final exam

Remote review for final exam

READING LIST

- Beck, J. (2015, February 27) How do archaeologists find sites? *Bone Broke*.
<https://bonebroke.org/2015/02/27/how-do-archaeologists-find-sites/>
- Beck, J. (2020). The human position: The potential of bioarchaeology for studies of inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory. In K. Lillios and P. Díaz-del-Río (Eds.), *Political matters in prehistory: Papers in honor of Antonio Gilman Guillén*. Bibliotheca Praehistorica Hispana.
- Bugos, C. (2019, November 26). The Myths of the Thanksgiving story and the lasting damage they imbue. *Smithsonian Magazine*. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/thanksgiving-myth-and-what-we-should-be-teaching-kids-180973655/>
- Cannon, K. P., & Boeka Cannon, M. (2004). Zooarchaeology and wildlife management in the greater Yellowstone ecosystem. In R. L. Lyman & K. Cannon (Eds.), *Zooarchaeology and conservation biology* (pp. 45–60). Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- Crabtree, S. A., Vaughn, L. J. S., & Crabtree, N. T. (2017). Reconstructing Ancestral Pueblo food webs in the southwestern United States. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 81, 116–127.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2017.03.005>
- De León, J. (2012). “Better to be hot than caught”: Excavating the conflicting roles of migrant material culture. *American Anthropologist*, 114(3), 477–495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1433.2012.01447.x>
- Feder, K. L. (2020). Prehistoric E.T. The fantasy of ancient astronauts. In *Frauds, myths, and mysteries: Science and pseudoscience in archaeology* (10th ed., pp. 196–219). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Fisher, C. (2020). Archaeology for sustainable agriculture. In *Journal of Archaeological Research* (Vol. 28). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-019-09138-5>
- Groesbeck, A. S., Rowell, K., Lepofsky, D., & Salomon, A. K. (2014). Ancient clam gardens increased shellfish production: Adaptive strategies from the past can inform food security today. *PLoS ONE*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091235>
- Harris, O. J. T., & Cipolla, C. (2017). Multi-species archaeology: People, plants and animals. In *Archaeological theory in the new millennium: Introducing current perspectives* (pp. 152–170). Basingstoke: Taylor & Francis.
- LaRoche, C. J., & Blakey, M. L. (1997). Seizing intellectual power: The dialogue at the New York African Burial Ground. *Historical Archaeology*, 31(3), 84–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03374233>
- Lentz, D. L., Dunning, N. P., Scarborough, V. L., & Grazioso, L. (2018). Imperial resource management at the ancient Maya city of Tikal: A resilience model of sustainability and collapse. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 52(August), 113–122.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2018.08.005>
- Leonard, L., Moss, J., Khan, A., & Knuckles, F. (2020, February 20). As College works to comply with NAGPRA, community interrogates institutional, academic history. *The Miscellany News*.
<https://miscellanynews.org/2020/02/20/news/vassar-stores-native-american-human-remains-violates-nagpra/>
- Morey, D. F. (2006). Burying key evidence: The social bond between dogs and people. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 33(2), 158–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2005.07.009>

- Moser, S. (2007). On disciplinary culture: Archaeology as fieldwork and its gendered associations. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, 14(3), 235–263.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-007-9033-5>
- O'Connor, T. (2013). Introduction. In *The archaeology of animal bones* (pp. 1–4). Thrupp: Sutton Publishing.
- O'Connor, T. (2013). Settling down: The domestication of animals and people. In *The archaeology of animal bones* (pp. 147–159). Thrupp: Sutton Publishing.
- Overholtzer, L., & Argueta, J. R. (2018). Letting skeletons out of the closet: the ethics of displaying ancient Mexican human remains. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 24(5), 508–530.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2017.1390486>
- Parker, E. A. (2016). The proliferation of pseudoarchaeology through “reality” television programming. In J. J. Card & D. S. Anderson (Eds.), *Lost city, found pyramid: Understanding alternative archaeologies and pseudoscientific practices* (pp. 149–166). Tuscaloosa: The University of Alabama Press.
- Rathje, W. L. & Murphy, C. (1992). Garbage and History In *Rubbish! The archaeology of garbage*. (pp. 30–52). Tuscon: University of Arizona Press.
- Rivera, M. (Producer) (2019, October 25). The Arch & Anth Podcast. Episode 64: How do sexism, racism and heterosexism affect archaeological knowledge about the past? Interview with Laura Heath-Stout. [Audio podcast]. <https://archandanth.com/episode-64-interview-with-laura-heath-stout/>
- Rivera, M. (Producer) (2020, June 24). The Arch & Anth Podcast. Episode 143: How do experts discover and study rock art in Southeast Asia? Interview with Noel Hidalgo Tan. [Audio podcast]. <https://archandanth.com/episode-143-interview-with-noel-hidalgo-tan/>
- Robb, J. (2009). Towards a critical Ötziography: Inventing prehistoric bodies. In H. Lambert & M. McDonald (Eds.), *Social bodies* (pp. 100–128). New York: Berghan Books.
- Schilling, T. (2012). Building Monks Mound, Cahokia, Illinois, A.D. 800-1400. *Journal of Field Archaeology*, 37(4), 302–313. <https://doi.org/10.1179/0093469012Z.00000000027>
- Steadman, D. W. (1995). Prehistoric extinctions of Pacific island birds: Biodiversity meets zooarchaeology. *Science*, 267(5201), 1123–1131.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.267.5201.1123>
- Thomas, J. T., & Waterman, A. J. (2013). Down the rabbit hole: the significance of Late Neolithic lagomorph figurines in anthropological perspective. *Archaeological Review from Cambridge*, 28(2), 113–131.
- Timmerman, N. A. (2020). Contested indigenous landscapes: Indian mounds and the political creation of the mythical “mound builder” race. *Ethnohistory*, 67(1), 75–95.
<https://doi.org/10.1215/00141801-7888741>
- Twiss, K. C. (2020). Identity: Food, affiliation, and distinction. In *The archaeology of food: Identity, politics, and ideology in the prehistoric and historic past* (pp. 129–154). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- White, W., & Draycott, C. (2020, July 7). Why the whiteness of archaeology is a problem. *Sapiens*.
<https://www.sapiens.org/archaeology/archaeology-diversity/>